

Forms Presentation

- Non-tabbed layout (Abi)

Hearings

Hearing Officers Management Citizens Management Schedules Management Hearings Management

Create Hearing Officer

Name *

Phone *

Area * Role *

Is Collective *

Yes

No

Authorization required for scheduling *

Yes

No

Address * Town *

[Submit](#)

Task: Edit Hearing Officer

Process: Hearing Officer Management ➔

Hearing Officers List

Name	Area	Role	Authorization	
Alexandre Gonçalves	Supervision	Supervisor	No	
Daniel Neves	Council	Architect	No	
Official Teste	Waters of Funchal	Supervisor	No	

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- Tabbed layout (Tim)

Hearings

Hearing Officers Management Citizens Management Schedules Management Hearings Management

Create Hearing Officer

Officer Details
Location Details

Name *

Phone *

Area * Role *

Is Collective *

Yes

No

Authorization required for scheduling *

Yes

No

[Submit](#)

Task: Edit Hearing Officer

Process: Hearing Officer Management ➔

Hearing Officers List

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Alexandre Gonçalves	Supervision	Supervisor	No	
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Hearings

Hearing Officers Management Citizens Management Schedules Management Hearings Management

Create Hearing Officer

Officer Details Location Details

Address * Town *

Submit

Task: Edit Hearing Officer

Process: Hearing Officer Management

Hearing Officers List

Name	Area	Role	Authorization
Alexandre Gonçalves	Supervision	Supervisor	No
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Tooltips for Form Fields:

- Always visible as text (Abi)

Hearings

Hearing Officers Management Citizens Management Schedules Management Hearings Management

Create Citizen

Name *

NIF * Email *

Phone * Suspended *

Submit

Task: Edit Citizen

Process: Citizen Management

Citizens List

Name	NIF	Email	Phone
Rui Mario	64245235	rui@mail.com	926838226
Diana Cabral	63445163	diana@mail.com	926883267
Município Teste	64245235	teste@mail.com	9237185

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- Hidden behind a "?" symbol (requiring hover) (Tim)

Hearings

Hearing Officers Management Citizens Management Schedules Management Hearings Management

Create Citizen

Name *

NIF * Email *

Phone * Suspended ? *

Submit

Task: Edit Citizen

Process: Citizen Management

Citizens List

Name	NIF	Email	Phone
Rui Mario	64245235	rui@mail.com	926838226
Diana Cabral	63445163	diana@mail.com	926883267
Município Teste	64245235	teste@mail.com	9237185

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Task Button Tooltips

- Visible (Abi)

Tarefa: Edit Citizen
Processo: Citizen Management
Dica: This is a tip!

- Non-visible tooltips for task-related buttons (Tim)

Tarefa: Edit Citizen
Processo: Citizen Management

UI Component Grouping

- Presence of grouping panels for organizing UI components (Abi)

Hearings

Hearing Officers Management Citizens Management Schedules Management Hearings Management

Create Schedule Block

Hearing Officer *

Start Date * End Date *

Start Time * End Time *

Day of the Week *

Duration *

Submit

Agenda Blocks

Tarefa: Edit Hearing Officer Scheduling Block
Processo: Manage Hearing Officer Schedule

Agenda Blocks List

Hearing Officer	Start Date	End Date	Day of the Week	Start Time	End Time	Duration
Alexandre Gonçalves	2024/11/5	2024/11/19	Tuesday	10:00	12:00	30
Daniel Neves	2024/11/6	2024/11/20	Wednesday	15:00	16:00	30
Official Teste	2024/11/12	2024/11/19	Tuesday	10:00	11:00	30

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Agenda Slots

Tarefa: Edit Hearing Slot
Processo: Manage Hearing Officer Schedule

Agenda Slots List

Hearing Officer	Day	Start Time	End Time	State
Alexandre Gonçalves	2024/11/05	10:00	10:30	Free
Alexandre Gonçalves	2024/11/05	10:30	11:00	Busy
Alexandre Gonçalves	2024/11/05	11:00	11:30	Free
Alexandre Gonçalves	2024/11/05	11:30	12:00	Free
Alexandre Gonçalves	2024/11/12	10:00	10:30	Free
Alexandre Gonçalves	2024/11/12	10:30	11:00	Free
Alexandre Gonçalves	2024/11/12	11:00	11:30	Free
Alexandre Gonçalves	2024/11/12	11:30	12:00	Free

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- Absence of grouping panels for organizing UI components (Tim)

Hearings

Hearing Officers Management Citizens Management Schedules Management Hearings Management

Create Schedule Block

Hearing Officer *

Start Date *

End Date *

Start Time *

End Time *

Day of the Week *

Duration *

[Submit](#)

Tarefa: Edit Hearing Officer Scheduling Block

Process: Manage Hearing Officer Schedule

Agenda Blocks List

Hearing Officer	Start Date	End Date	Day of the Week	Start Time	End Time	Duration
Alexandro Gonçalves	2024/11/5	2024/11/19	Tuesday	10:00	12:00	30
Daniel Neves	2024/11/6	2024/11/20	Wednesday	15:00	16:00	30
Official Teste	2024/11/12	2024/11/19	Tuesday	10:00	11:00	30

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Tarefa: Edit Hearing Slot

Process: Manage Hearing Officer Schedule

Agenda Slots List

Hearing Officer	Day	Start Time	End Time	State
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Alexandro Gonçalves	2024/11/05	11:30	12:00	Free
Alexandro Gonçalves	2024/11/12	10:00	10:30	Free
Alexandro Gonçalves	2024/11/12	10:30	11:00	Free
Alexandro Gonçalves	2024/11/12	11:00	11:30	Free
Alexandro Gonçalves	2024/11/12	11:30	12:00	Free

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